

METALLIZATION OF COMPOSITE AERONAUTICS STRUCTURE THROUGH ROBOTIZED DEPOSITION COLD SPRAY TECHNOLOGIES

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ABSTRACT

Unlike their metal counterparts, composite structures do not readily conduct away the electrical currents generated by lightning strikes. Cost reduction and expected production in aeronautics require automated manufacturing process. The development of an automated technology to metallize polymer based composite for lightning strike protection is the aim of the CO3 project. In this study, thermal and electrical conductivities of composites are achieved by the cold spray deposition of a metallic (Cu or Al) coating. The critical points to be addressed were substrate erosion during cold spray, lack of polymer-metal adhesion as well as poor deposition efficiency.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 State of the art and CO3 project positioning

Polymers and Carbon Fiber Reinforced Composites (CFRCs) have a great potential application in aircraft structures for light weighting purposes and its resistance to corrosion. As a drawback, these materials exhibit vulnerabilities to lightning strikes due to their limited electrical conductivity, which can result in serious physical damage effects such as erosion, ablation or entire explosion of the structure [1, 2]. Airplane skin is divided in several zones, as shown in Figure 1 on the right, classified depending on the potential strength of the lightning strike received, which is a function of the geometry and of the position of the part within the structure. Parts located near the extremities and having high curvature are exposed to the most intense strikes (zones 1A). The intensity decreases as the code increase (1A, 1B, 1C, 2A, etc.) [3, 4]. To get flying certification, parts have to withstand specific lightning strike tests in laboratory, where the effect of a true strike is experimentally simulated by dedicated systems. The severity of parameters of the test (tension/current waves applied to the part) depends on the abovementioned code for the zone of exposure. Actually, the most widespread solution for lightning strike protection is the application of metallic meshes, available in different materials (typically Al, Cu or bronze) and with different mass per unit surface to adapt to the different zones. In many parts of the airplane, metallic meshes are still manually laid up. Since composite manufacturing is following the road to full automation, especially for cost reduction, the metallization should follow as well.

Warmer spraying technologies, such as plasma, flame, electric arc spray for example, although highly efficient, do not work properly with temperature sensitive powders and substrate materials [5, 6]. Cold Spray is proposed as an alternative technique, mainly because of the lower process temperatures and its ability to obtain dense and non-oxidized metallic coatings, two important factors for electrical conductivity. The challenge of applying a metallic coating onto CFRCs by cold spray relies in finding suitable powders and spraying conditions to prevent fibres damage and erosion of the substrate material, as already shown by numerous researches. To give a quick literature overview of these studies, in 2006 Sturgeon et al. [7] cold sprayed aluminum powder on a short carbon fiber reinforced PEEK. Adherent and dense coatings could be achieved using helium as a spraying gas. However, it must be stressed that the composite made with short carbon fibers differs significantly with respect to continuous fiber materials which are mostly used in airplane manufacturing. In a similar study Zhou et al. [8], still using short carbon fibers/PEEK composite, a high pressure cold spray system was used to spray aluminum and copper. For the successful bonding of copper particles, an aluminum bond coat was used. In the same context, Malachowska et al. in 2018 [9] achieved the metallization of PA6 and PC with copper particles, via a tin interlayer. Another way to produce cold spray metal coatings on polymers and composites was based on deposition of few polymer particle layers that fused with the substrate [10, 11]. In parallel, several works [6, 12] recommended to cold spray mixed Al-Sn powders with a lower melting point material, at 300°C for various pressures (0.4 MPa to 1MPa). The work showed the difficulty to achieve dense and adherent coatings onto both carbon fibers and epoxy based materials. The use of mixture powders of metal and polymer powders was shown to be an interesting way to limit fiber failure and to produce adherent and electrically conductive coatings [13].

In the present study, different strategies were tested, alone and in combination between them, to achieve the goal of CFRC metallization: Protective Polymer Film (PPF), Supercritical Nitrogen Deposition (SND), Low Pressure Cold Spray (LPCS) of mixed Aluminum and PEEK powders, High Pressure Cold Spray (HPCS).

Figure 1: On the left, materials used in the outer skin of Boeing 787 (left); airplane lightning zones following SAE Aerospace Recommended Practice ARP 5414, 1999 (middle) and the targeted CO3 demonstrator (right)

2. EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Materials and methods

Aluminum and copper powders were used as feedstock materials for the surface metallization of CFRCs by cold spray and SCND. In some LPCS tests they were mixed with PEEK powders to produce metal-polymer composite coatings. The powders used are listed in Table 1. SEM images of powders used in the present study are shown in Figure 2.

Table 1. Feedstock powders.

Metals	Size	Polymer	Size
Al (99.9% high purity) from Toyal	20-50 μm	PEEK Vicote702 from Vitrex	26-88 μm
Cu (99.95% high purity) from Safina	15-38 μm		

Figure 2. SEM top view images of powders: (a) aluminum Toyal, (b) Copper Safina, mixed with 20%vol. PEEK, (c) PEEK Vicote702.

Three main physical coating properties were identified as the most relevant for the final application: superficial mass, adhesion and electrical conductivity. All these are finally related to coating microstructures that were characterized by scanning electron microscopy (ZEISS Sigma 300). Cross-section images were used for quantitative phase analysis by image analysis open source routines implemented in Python (Simple Morphological Image Library, <http://smil.cmm.mines-paristech.fr>). The tensile bond strength of the coatings was tested according to ASTM C633-1 norm “Standard Test Method for Adhesion or Cohesion Strength of Thermal Spray Coatings”, using an Instron tensile testing machine. This test consists in quantitatively measuring the resistance of the coating-substrate assemblies applying a growing pull-off force until rupture. The Van der Pauw method [15] was used for the measurement of electrical surface conductivity. Measurements were realized with a dedicated set up, made by a measuring chamber ”HFS600E-PB4” from Linkam, with four measuring tips (Figure 3, on the right), coupled to a Keithley unit allowing current generation and voltage measurement. The maximal current was 1 A.

Figure 3. On the left, schematic view of the Van der Pauw method; at the center, picture of one of the tested samples; on the right, picture of the measuring set up.

2.2 Protective polymer layers (PPL)

Due to the intrinsic thermos-mechanical properties of high performance thermoset compare to thermoplastic, the erosion damage at the composite surface could occurs during deposition inducing surface defect as well as composite internal damage. This phenomenon highlights the lack of thermoset-metal adhesion as well as a poor deposition efficiency. This achieved work investigated and optimized the in-situ surface functionalization through thin thermoplastic layer incorporated during the manufacturing of the CFRP substrate. An analysis the relationship between the composite manufacturing conditions, in particular the cure state of the matrix and the resulting thermoplastic coating adhesion properties is proposed, as preliminary studied in the literature. In our work, a 25, 50 and 300 μm PEEK film at an amorphous and semi-crystalline state Aptiv®2000 from Victrex® are co-cured with the thermoset composite. The amorphous state will foster the migration of thermoset pre-polymer molecules into the thermoplastic film and will improved significantly the resulting adhesion through micro-mechanical interlocking. Through a surface treatment by N₂/O₂(80/20) atmospheric plasma,

the wettability of the PEEK film is improved through a cleaning and chemical activation. In addition, the plasma treatment generate a growth of the surface roughness of the PEEK film. The effect of the cure rate of the RTM6-2 resin as well as the post plasma treatment waiting time (Cf. Figure 4) is investigated through mechanical test (film peeling) and optical analysis (Cf. Figure 5)

The result of this work is the proposition of a protective polymers layer, suitable for thermoset composite, enabling the automated metallization by a spraying technology.

Figure 4: Protective polymer surface preparation

Figure 5: Effect of cure kinetic on interphase between the thermoset composite and the polymeric protective layer by SEM (left) and AFM (right)

2.3 Equipment

The **SND technique** consists in the addition of copper powder particles to a Super Critical Nitrogen jet at very high pressure, flowing out of a specific nozzle. Particles are then accelerated at high velocities and sprayed to the substrate surface at low temperatures. This process can be used as a new and colder spraying technique or as an innovative surface preparation, before cold spraying the conductive coating.

In **cold spray**, the heated and pressurized gas accelerates powder particles to be sprayed through a converging/diverging “de Laval” nozzle, reaching supersonic speeds during its expansion. When particles impact on the substrate, they can adhere, forming a coating by a building-up process. The kinetic energy of the particles, rather than high temperature, allow particles to plastically deform and bond together to produce coatings. Due to the relatively low temperatures, cold spray avoids or minimizes many deleterious shortcomings of traditional thermal spray methods such as high-temperature oxidation, evaporation, melting, crystallization, residual stresses [14]. Two types of equipment can be found today on the market: **low pressure** systems (limited to 0.8-1.5 MPa, depending on the model) and more performing **high pressure** ones (reaching up to 6 MPa and 1100°C). HPCS experiments were carried out using a CGT Kinetiks 4000/47 system (with pressure up to 4 MPa and temperature up to 850°C) with nitrogen gaz. A PBI (Polymer) was been used for spraying aluminum powder, while a 24TC (Tungsten Carbide) nozzle for spraying copper. The gun was mounted on a Reis robotic system RVL 26. The LPCS system used was a DYCOMET model 523 (Akkrum, The Netherlands) operating with compressed air, with pressure up to 0.6 MPa and temperature up to 600°C. LPCS system differs from the high pressure one for a different

powder injection point, located downstream to the nozzle throat, as well as for the range of pressure-temperature couples that can be used.

3. RESULTS

3.1 Supercritical nitrogen deposition

The first trials of SCND onto thermoset based CFRCs were done with Cu powder and varying process parameters. No Cu deposition could be obtained. Only few particles could stick to the composite, while in many areas the surface of the material was damaged. Broken fibers and damaged polymer matrix are visible. Copper particles impacted at high speed and, due to their low temperatures, they were rigid enough to erode the substrate. Better results were obtained thanks to a PPF. A PEEK film was applied on CFRC surface before copper SCND. In this configuration, it was possible to deposit a larger number of particles per unit surface and to preserve carbon fibers, as shown in Figure 6. On the left, the SEM top view illustrates the density of Cu particles while, on the right, the SEM cross section shows that Cu particles penetrated into the PEEK PPF without reaching the underlying carbon fibers. The ductility of the thermoplastic PEEK, in fact, allowed particle incrustation on the surface. Its plastic deformation absorbed the high kinetic energy of impinging Cu particles and avoided their rebounding. At the same time, it effectively protected the fragile thermoset based material. Nevertheless, despite a considerable density of copper particles could be achieved, these coatings were not good electrical conductors. In fact, the measured electrical resistivity was in the order of $108 \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$, to be compared with a reference value on copper tape of $2.9 \cdot 10^{-6} \Omega \cdot \text{cm}$. During the process, impinging particles could hardly form a sufficient bonding to already deposited metallic particles and, thus, rebounded away. Electrical conductivity suffered from the lack of a continuous path into the metallic phase for electric conduction.

Figure 6: SEM images of CFRC sample with PPF after SCND of copper particles (1 pass, 10 m.min-1); on the left, top view; on the right, cross-section of the same sample.

3.2 High pressure cold spray

HPCS tests were conducted using copper and aluminum feedstock powders, on substrates with PPF. In fact, preliminary tests on bare substrates resulted in erosion and carbon fiber damage. Copper coatings were cold sprayed at high pressure onto thermoset based CFRCs with a 50 µm PEEK PPF. A large range of spraying parameters was tested (temperature between 400 and 500°C, pressure between 0.8 and 1.4 MPa, standoff distance within 30-110 mm, transverse speed in the range 200-400 mm.s-1). Figure 7 on the right shows a SEM cross-sectional image of a copper coating. Cu particles possessed high kinetic energy and could penetrate deeply into the PEEK PPF, whose final thickness resulted largely decreased. The extended interface developed suggests a good anchoring of the coating to the substrate. Measurements shows a tensile strength between 5 to 8 MPa depending of the process conditions and a failure through

the coating. Coated sample showed different colors with the variations of spraying parameters, from paly pink to red-brown, passing by orange due to various oxidation level.

Figure 7: Various oxidation level depending on stand-off distance (right), tensile test sample after failure (middle) and SEM cross sections of HPCS coatings on thermoset based CFRC substrates with PPF (right)

3.3 Low pressure cold spray

The first LPCS tests onto PEEK based CFRCs, with aluminum and copper as feedstock powders, were not successful, because the exposed carbon fibers were too sensitive to damage by high speed impacting particles. The application of a PEEK PPF showed to be a viable solution to protect the fibers and made possible the LPCS of both thermoplastic and thermoset based CFRCs. Nevertheless, those coatings were more porous and with a seemingly reduced anchoring in the PPF than those obtained by HPCS, resulting in poorer electrical conductivity and adhesion. In successive LPCS experiments, an irregularly shaped PEEK powder (Vicote702) was mixed with Cu or with Al powders to produce metal-polymer composite coatings onto different thermoset and thermoplastic based CFRCs, with or without PPF. The influence of cold spray parameters (gas pressure, temperature and standoff distance) was investigated. Figure 8, on the right, shows a SEM cross-sectional image of Cu-20%vol.PEEK onto a PEEK based CFRC with PPF. Copper particles seem to be embedded into a polymer matrix (co-sprayed PEEK powder), which resulted to be an effective coating binder, promoting the adhesion and cohesion of the coating. Only low values of copper content in the coating could be achieved, estimated by image analysis. The highest was 50% vol. of Cu, in the coating shown in Fig. 9 on the right. Electrical conductivity is thus expected to be low. Figure 8, on the left, shows a SEM cross-sectional image of Al-20%vol. PEEK composite coating. In this case, the metal content is much higher and the electrical resistivity was measured to be $7.55 \cdot 10^{-5} \Omega\text{m}$.

Figure 8. SEM cross sections of LPCS polymer-metal composite coatings on thermoplastic CFRC substrates, on the left Al-PEEK 20%vol, on the right Cu-PEEK 20%vol.

LPCS of composites metal-polymer coatings seemed more promising with Al powders than with Cu powders. This solution would be even more interesting for the final application if it

would be possible to spray the composite on bare substrates, without the need of a PPF. Thus, some tests were done on thermoplastic based CFRCs with and without PEI PPF. In both cases, a thick Al-20% vol. PEEK composite coating was achieved by optimizing the process parameters, as shown in Figure 9. showing a remarkable value for electrical conductivity.

Figure 9: SEM cross sections of LPCS Al-PEEK 20%vol. coatings, on the left with PPF PEI, on the right without PPF.

3.4 Trajectory generation tool development

To achieve the full-scale demonstrator coating, a 3D numerical demonstrator development have been performed to simulate the paths of the robot that will manage the cold spray gun during the cold spraying process. An algorithm for an « automatic generation of projection paths » based on the geometry of complex 3D parts has been created and developed. Trajectories are now automatically calculate and generate the depending on the surface or geometry of the part to be treated, to manage projection parameters and finally permit virtual and real multi-trial execution.

The demonstrator is currently in its final test and improvement phase, as recent advances are showing promising results such as a successful execution of the projections in the virtual cell by a KUKA robot (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Illustration of trajectories induces coating defects due to overlapping effect

4. CONCLUSIONS

Various efforts have been made to metallize polymer-based composites via different strategies, with the purpose of obtaining an electrical conductive coating with good adhesion. Four technologies and some of their combinations were tested to metallize CFRC substrates: i) application of a Protective Polymer Film (PPF), ii) SuperCritical Nitrogen Deposition (SCND), iii) Low Pressure Cold Spray (LPCS), iv) High Pressure Cold Spray (HPCS). The PPF alone

is non-conductive, so it must be employed in combination with the other technologies. A quantitative characterization of the film adhesion has yet to be performed. SCND, although not capable in these first experiments of producing a conductive metallic layer, showed a potential interest as an innovative technology for surface preparation before cold spraying, in particular after the application of a PPF. Cold spray technology viability for the metallization of thermoset and thermoplastic based CFRCs was demonstrated for both HPCS and LPCS. Copper coatings by HPCS after the application of PPF seemed the most promising solution for thermoset based CFRCs. In the case of thermoplastic based materials, LPCS of Al-PEEK mixed powders without any PPF was retained as the most interesting solution explored up to now. In the next phases of the project a complete optimization of spraying materials and parameters will be performed as well as the manufacturing of several full demonstrator enabling the lightning test evaluation.

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6. REFERENCES

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